

Search Trends: “*The Clap*” versus “*Gonorrhea*” in Economically Opposite States

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Topic: Terminology referring to Gonorrhea

Title: Search Trends: “*The Clap*” versus “*Gonorrhea*” in Economically Opposite States

Objectives: To analyze search trends in Mississippi versus Massachusetts, with both slang and technical terms referring to gonorrhea.

Background: Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) produce over twenty million cases per year. However, there appears to be a gap in analyzing how wealthy environments influence the types of searches that are more prevalent among users of Google when it comes to finding information on STDs. Analyzing search trends to look at whether colloquial or technical terms are more common in certain states could give insight into whether wealthier states have more effective sexual education programs.

Methods: I generated data on search trends comparing the terms *The Clap* and *Gonorrhea* in Mississippi and Massachusetts through the Google Trends platform. All categories of web searches from October 2008 to June 2025 were considered for the specified terms. I then exported the relevant information to Google Sheets in order to create graphs displaying the overall trends, as well as calculating the mean search popularity for each term and state per month.

Results: I analyzed Mississippi and Massachusetts because they had the lowest and highest median household incomes, respectively (based on the 2023 US census). On average, in both Mississippi and Massachusetts, the term *Gonorrhea* was searched for about four times more than the term *The Clap* was searched for. Additionally, the amount that each term was searched for, on average, per month, was approximately the same for both states.

Conclusions: The technical terminology *Gonorrhea* appeared more often than the colloquial terminology, *The Clap*, in both Mississippi and Massachusetts. In the future, scientists could directly survey the populations in order to evaluate the language and understanding that Mississippi and Massachusetts residents actually have in relation to gonorrhea, in order to evaluate the states’ sexual education programs, and possibly improve them.

Keyword 1: Gonorrhea

Keyword 2: Search Trends

Keyword 3: The Clap

Keyword 4: Household Income

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